

EXAMINING THE IMPACT OF A FIVE-WEEK ONLINE MINDFULNESS-BASED STRESS REDUCTION (MBSR) PROGRAM ON ACADEMIC BURNOUT AMONG SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Examining the Impact of a Five-week Online Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction (MBSR) Program on Academic Burnout among Senior High School Students

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Abstract

Recent studies have highlighted the efficacy of mindfulness training in alleviating stress and anxiety among students while also enhancing coping mechanisms and emotional regulation skills. This one-group pretest-posttest study aimed to assess the impact of a five-week online mindfulness-based stress reduction program on academic burnout in senior high school students from Our Lady of Perpetual Help School in Pasig City. The study utilized the Oldenburg Burnout Inventory for students (OLBI-S) to measure burnout, focusing on its dimensions of exhaustion and disengagement. Descriptive statistics and paired samples t-tests were conducted using SPSS® due to the study's small sample size. Results indicated no significant differences between pretest and posttest scores in disengagement and overall academic burnout. However, there was a statistically significant decrease in scores on the exhaustion subscale post-intervention, suggesting that the mindfulness program may specifically mitigate feelings of physical and emotional depletion associated with academic demands. These findings contribute to the growing body of evidence supporting the potential of mindfulness interventions in educational settings to target specific aspects of burnout among high school students.

Keywords: *academic burnout, mindfulness-based stress reduction, COVID-19, online and distance learning*

Introduction

The coronavirus disease (COVID-19) threw a wrench halfway into the Philippine academic year in early March 2020, leaving institutions unprepared (CNN, 2020; Official Gazette, 2020; The Guardian, 2020). In the Philippines, online and distance learning delivery faced challenges that put academic pressure on teachers, students, parents, and other stakeholders to continue with education. This study aims to find avenues to understand whether a mindful-based stress-reduction program would benefit learners and provide them with better management skills for academic stress, exhaustion, and disengagement. School administrators resorted to online distance learning (ODL) across all levels to prevent the virus's spread in school buildings and campuses. ODL entails instructors using smartphones, tablets, laptops, or computers to connect with their students via the internet and cascade academic tasks from there. While there are advantages to ODL, there are also pains that both students and instructors have to deal with (Gilbert, 2015).

Students in underdeveloped countries like Pakistan have found it challenging to access the internet and ask for real-time responses (Adnan, 2020). Di Pietro, Costa, Karpiński & Mazza (2020) predicted in their technical report that students will spend less time learning and more time on homework, which is questionable in terms of academic effectiveness. Among the significant barriers students face brought about by ODL and the pandemic are academic stress and anxiety (Baticulon et al., 2020; Tee et al., 2020). Baticulon et al. (2020, pp. 12) highlighted in their findings that Filipino medical students are mentally unprepared for such a drastic shift in learning mode, thereby causing anxiety, psychological distress, and burnout. Similarly, a study on Harvard dentistry students revealed that as soon as ODL and the lockdown were enforced, burnout increased, and engagement went down (Chen et al., 2020).

It can be surmised that academic or learning burnout is a common denominator in studies that involve ODL amid COVID-19. Maslach and Jackson (1981), who pioneered the widely used Maslach Burnout Index, defined burnout as a "psychological syndrome due to prolonged job stress that results in a three-component set of symptoms: feeling diminished emotional resources, feeling cynical and bad about one's clients, and feeling unhappy about oneself and dissatisfaction with one's productivity at work."

While the definition mentions only jobs, the context of burnout expands to students' experiences as their academic load is also recognized as work. The three dimensions are then translated to exhaustion, cynicism, and academic inefficacy (Lee et al., 2020).

One factor that explains high academic burnout levels is students' social and familial support (Zhang et al., 2020). As the lockdown limits social interaction, the students' social spheres close in on them, leaving only room for studies and tests. Correspondingly, in Son et al.'s (2020) study, reasons for a decline in mental health range from having disrupted sleeping patterns to profusely worrying about academic performance. Students' belief in their ability to carry out a task and perform well also contributes to higher burnout levels (BiLge et al., 2014).

With the various factors ingrained in burnout, it's difficult to distinguish which element one should pay attention to. Interestingly enough, some studies point to mindfulness having a protective effect on burnout. Yıldız-Akyol and Demir's (2019) research on senior students in Turkey proved that burnout negatively predicts mindfulness. The authors recommended more institutions to promote mindfulness practices to students and instructors alike.

Mindfulness practices have also proven useful in the context of exam-related anxiety and stress. Studies have found that a mindfulness training program has reduced test-related stress and anxiety. Additionally, the training significantly contributed to students' coping skills and emotional regulation (Ross et al., 2020; Shahidi et al., 2017).

A standard mindfulness training program that has been practiced since the 1980s is the mindfulness-based stress reduction (MBSR) program pioneered by John Kabat-Zin in 1979. This was initially intended to alleviate the pain of chronically ill patients through self-regulation of emotions and stress. Presently, MBSR has been practiced by different populations to relieve pain and suffering, and target specific health concerns (Nehra et al., 2013).

In a meta-analysis of studies, it was revealed how effective MBSR is to different clinical measures such as depression, distress, and anxiety. However, the authors cautioned that the program must not be modified or shortened, and the respondents must be highly committed to the program until the last session (Khoury et al., 2015).

In the context of burnout, experimental trials of MBSR and mindfulness classes have been conducted on healthcare professionals since the healthcare field demands extended hours and unrelenting efforts to improve their patient's conditions. Post-training and follow-up assessments reveal significantly improved burnout and mindfulness scores among the respondents (Duarte & Pinto-Gouveia, 2016; Goodman & Schorling, 2012; Verweij et al., 2016).

However, no studies tried to conduct MBSR or mindfulness training in the academic setting to reduce academic burnout. Thereupon, the authors purported to study the effect of a modified online mindfulness-based stress reduction program on senior high school students in Our Lady of Perpetual Help School. The result was measured using a pretest and posttest experimental research method.

Since the pandemic caught almost all Filipino students off guard with very little time to adjust, it's imperative to seek how students cope with the new arrangement and discover interventions to make the transition as easy as possible. Results will be provided to the institution for the academic stakeholders to take action on the relevant aspects of students' academic load.

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized a pretest-posttest type of research design. This research design includes measurements that are taken on individuals both before and after they received treatment or have been exposed to a condition. In this study, the researchers followed three steps: (1) administer a pretest for burnout, (2) implement a five-week online mindfulness-based stress reduction program, and (3) re-administer a post-test for burnout. The differences attributed to the application of the treatment are then evaluated by comparing the pretest and post-test scores.

Respondents

The study population included all the senior high school students of Our Lady of Perpetual Help School. The Online Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction program was administered to 48 senior high school students currently enrolled at OLPHS for the school year 2020 to 2021. Samples were selected through purposive sampling. The nature and benefits of the study were discussed with the respondents. They were also given online consent forms for their voluntary participation and permission forms to approve their parents. From this sample, 24 are male, and 24 are female, whose ages ranged between 16 to 18.

Instruments

The Oldenburg Burnout Inventory for Students (OLBI-S)

To measure academic burnout, the researchers used the adapted version of the Oldenburg Burnout Inventory for students (OLBI-S) (Reis et al., 2015). The adapted version is based on the English version of the original OLBI (Demerouti et al., 2010). The researchers obtained permission to use the tool from all the concerned authors through email.

It consists of 16 items measuring two dimensions of burnout: disengagement and exhaustion. The first half, eight items, measures disengagement (e.g., "I always find new and interesting aspects in my studies"); and the other half, eight items, measures exhaustion (e.g., "There are days when I feel tired before I arrive to class or start studying"). It has a scale ranging from 1 (strongly agree) to 6 (strongly disagree). Both subscales were found to be reliable: exhaustion (Cronbach's $\alpha = .87$) and disengagement (Cronbach's $\alpha = .81$). (Reis et al., 2015).

Procedure

The present study followed a paired-group pretest-posttest design to investigate the effect of a five-week online mindfulness-based stress reduction program on burnout. Permission from the school principal/chairman of the board was first obtained before conducting the study. All the relevant information, including the objectives and importance of the research project, was included in the permission letter sent to the school.

The study proceeded after the respondents and their parents completed the consent and assent forms through Google forms. The sessions were conducted every Wednesday during their Homeroom and Guidance period. Before administering the online MBSR program, the respondents completed the baseline measure, pretest for burnout. One week following the program, all the respondents repeated the measurement of burnout for the posttest. After the posttest measure, the data analysis followed.

Program

The administered Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction program is an online version compressed into five weeks. The researchers used the Palouse Mindfulness – Online MBSR Program created by Sir Dave Potter, a fully certified MBSR instructor, and is based on the program founded by Dr. Jon Kabat-Zinn at the University of Massachusetts Medical School. (Potter, Online MBSR/Mindfulness (Free)) Permission was obtained from the author.

Due to time limitations and unforeseen events (i.e., holiday break and typhoon), the researchers compressed the eight-week program into a five-week program. The researchers administered the first three weeks in synchronous sessions every Wednesday. The last two weeks were in asynchronous sessions. The respondents were provided weekly materials, including instructional videos, readings, and daily formal and informal practices through a shared Google Drive. Researchers attended live to the respondents' questions during the synchronous sessions and through Facebook, Messenger group chat during the asynchronous sessions.

Overall, the five-week online MBSR program consists of Raisin Meditation, Body Scan, Mindful Yoga, Sitting Meditation, Turning Towards Meditation, Mountain and Lake Meditations, and Loving-kindness Meditation.

Data Analysis

Due to the study's small sample size, mainly descriptive statistics and t-tests were produced using the SPSS® tool. Using a paired samples t-test analysis, the study's design allowed for comparing the pretest and the posttest scores with the MBSR classes as an intervention.

According to Zumbo and Jennings (2002), the paired samples t-test can compare two different means of data from related samples as long as the respondents are identified.

There was a 6-week interval between tests. In the case of measuring burnout in the study, the intervention aims to lower the posttest results than the pretest.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. *Baseline characteristics (n=48) of the respondents*

Characteristics	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Sex		
Male	24	50%
Female	24	50%
Age		
16 y/o	16	33.33%
17 y/o	29	60.42%
18 y/o	3	6.25%
Grade Level		
Gr.11	33	68.75%
Gr. 12	15	31.25%
Strand		
Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM)	12	25%
General Academic Strand (GAS)	36	75%

Table 1 shows the profile of the respondents in terms of sex, age, grade level, and strand. 50% of the respondents are male, and 50% are female. The majority of them, 60.42%, are 17 years old, 33.33% are 16 years old, and the rest, 6.25%, are 18 years old. There were 33 (68.7%) Grade 11 students and 15 (31.25%) Grade 12 students who participated in the study. Twelve (25%) of them are enrolled in Accounting, Business, and Management strand, while the other 36 (75%) of them are enrolled in the General Academic Strand.

Table 2. *Pre and post-test differences across characteristics of the respondents*

	Pre-test Mean (SD)	Post-test Mean (SD)	t-Stat	p-value
Sex				
Male (n=24)	3.17 (0.36)	3.07 (0.27)	1.12	0.28
Female (n=24)	3.22 (0.42)	3.17 (0.40)	0.46	0.65
Age				
16 y/o (n=16)	3.20 (0.49)	2.97 (0.30)	1.57	0.12
17 y/o (n=29)	3.22 (0.33)	3.24 (0.31)	-0.22	0.82
18 y/o (n=3)	3.38 (0.44)	2.88 (0.22)	2.24	0.15
Grade Level				
11 (n=33)	3.23 (0.36)	3.13 (0.32)	1.23	0.22
12 (n=15)	3.13 (0.45)	3.10 (0.39)	0.17	0.87

	Strand			
ABM (n=12)	3.21 (0.37)	3.14 (0.31)	0.53	0.60
GAS (n=36)	3.20 (0.40)	3.12 (0.35)	0.91	0.37

Table 2 indicates additional findings of the pretest and posttest differences across the characteristics of the respondents. Based on the results, no significant differences were found between pretest and posttest measures across all the characteristics of the respondents. These findings are in line with prior research indicating that gender did not have a significant effect on mindfulness levels (Alomari, 2023). However, some literature reports that MBSR helps in reducing depressive symptoms among young people with various levels of depression severity (Chi et al., 2018), alleviating anxiety symptoms in young people (Zhou et al., 2020), and an effective and sustainable stress-countering approach in students (An et al., 2022). On the other hand, no present evidence would support the moderating effects of other factors, such as grade level and the strand of the MBSR program.

Tables 2 and 3 show the results for the OLBI-S scores for pretest and posttest measures for comparison. A paired sample t-test was used to analyze the data. It presents the results Mean, SD, t Stat, and p-value.

Table 3. *OLBI-S scores before and after the MBSR sessions of the respondents*

<i>n=48</i>	<i>Pre-test Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Post-test Mean (SD)</i>	<i>t-Stat</i>	<i>p-value</i>
Overall academic burnout	3.20 (0.39)	3.12 (0.34)	1.89	0.06
Disengagement	3.02 (0.43)	3.04 (0.38)	-0.27	0.79
Exhaustion	3.38 (0.43)	3.21 (0.41)	3.22	0.00*

*0.05 sig

For Table 3, no significant differences were found between the pretest and post-test scores for both the total academic burnout and disengagement. However, the total academic burnout has a slight decrease, which the online MBSR program can possibly account for conducted in-between time points. On the other hand, there is a significant difference between the pretest ($M= 3.38$, $SD= 0.43$) and posttest ($M= 3.21$, $SD= 0.41$) measures in the exhaustion subscale. This implies that online MBSR improved the exhaustion management ability of students by learning mindfulness.

In general, the present research's findings negate the study of Anand and Sharma (2011), which provides evidence for the effectiveness of the MSBR program in reducing academic stress, difficulties with peers, and emotional symptoms such as anger, sadness, frustration, anxiety, fear etc and improving their academic-self concept. Moreover, it contradicts Jaismin's et. al (2023) study, which highlighted that academic anxiety and subjective well-being improved significantly with the MBI intervention.

Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction Program

This study's mindfulness-based stress reduction program is an online and 100% free mindfulness program by a certified MBSR instructor. It is based on the program founded by Jon Kabat-Zinn at the University of Massachusetts Medical School. The Palouse mindfulness program is designed to be an eight-week program, but given the time constraints, the researchers compressed the program into a five-week program instead.

The Palouse Mindfulness Program's administration was on a weekly schedule, every Wednesday from 7:00 AM - 8:00 AM, via Google Meet. The researchers, on alternating schedules, conducted the Palouse Mindfulness program. Aside from the synchronous sessions, the students were given worksheets, video clips, and program sheets to monitor their self-paced progress.

In the last week of the program, the video clip and materials were uploaded to Google Drive and sent to the students since it was not possible to conduct a synchronous session due to the effect of Typhoon Ulysses.

Disengagement

Academic disengagement can be defined as a multi-faceted, complex, yet fluid state with a combination of behavioral, emotional, and cognitive domains (Chipchase et al., 2017). Online teaching and learning appear to contribute to the level of disengagement of students. The 2014 Australian FYES revealed that 35% of the students said that they have not engaged with online discussion groups compared to 19% for face-to-face learning (Krause K.-L & Armitage L., 2016).

In relation, OLPHS is new to online teaching and learning mode, beginning only in August 2020. With only about four months of online teaching and learning, both teachers and students may have difficulties adapting to the abrupt change caused by the pandemic. Moreover, despite the schedule given during the homeroom and guidance program, students could not fully participate due to the unstable internet connection at the location.

In the last week of the mindfulness-based stress reduction program, Santolan, Pasig City, where the students are located, was heavily affected by Typhoon Ulysses - electricity and internet connections were cut or unstable.

In Table 3, the researchers noted no significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the students. The researchers did not see a significant change in scores after administering the mindfulness-based stress reduction program among the students. Due to the school's shift in online learning delivery, students are reportedly not as engaged in face-to-face learning. Moreover, the respondents' difficulties during online learning include weak internet connectivity and an electric outage in Santolan, Pasig City. Additionally,

asynchronous learning mode lessens the interaction and engagement between fellow students and teachers.

Exhaustion

Pines and Aronson (1981) describe physical exhaustion as characterized by low energy and chronic fatigue, whereas emotional exhaustion refers to being depleted of one's emotional resources. Reduced personal accomplishment refers to feelings of decline in one's competence and productivity and a lowered sense of efficacy, representing the self-evaluation component of burnout (Maslach, 1998).

The results presented in Table 3 showed that there is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores for the OLBI-S exhaustion subscale.

Due to the sudden shift from face-to-face learning to online delivery of understanding of many schools in Metro Manila, OLPHS reduced its number of months for the school year - from August 2020 to April 2021 - to a total of nine months compared to the regular ten months. In this regard, the teaching methods need to be compressed, and modules with activities need to be disseminated and submitted at an earlier rate in the first few months with the additional stress in adjusting to the new normal in education.

The significant difference in the pretest and posttest results shows us that there is an effect on the mindfulness-based stress reduction program. Many of the topics of mindfulness-based stress reduction are better stress management by being able to manage time and as well as find rest between workloads. Additionally, the students' adjustment from the first weeks of classes shifted to understanding one's thinking and actions.

Overall Academic Burnout

Student burnout is defined as: "students in the learning process, because of course stress, course load or other psychological factors, display a state of emotional exhaustion, a tendency to depersonalization, and a feeling of low personal accomplishment." (Yang, 2004)

Student burnout may be related to academic workload, academic factors such as class engagement, exhaustion in the online delivery system, and external factors such as familial relationships and peer support.

Table 3 shows us that there is no significant difference in the pretest and posttest of the Oldenburg Burnout Inventory for students. Still, there is a slight decrease in their scores, which may be affiliated with the mindfulness-based stress reduction program's introduction and administration. Given the limitations of time, it is noted that there is a chance that more prolonged exposure and better execution of the program with consistent follow-ups can increase student mindfulness, thus decreasing burnout. As a result, there is potential for the MBSR program to be efficient in lessening burnout given that there is time dedicated to the program and monitoring of students regularly, as well as finding better tools to assess the current mental health needs of the senior high school students.

Despite the result of Table 3 showing that there is no significant difference in the overall academic burnout of the senior high school students of OLPHS, it is still a good practice to conduct programs that better understand the needs of the students and have better foundations in mental health programs directed towards the reduction of stress which may result to anxiety and depression if left unnoticed. Moreover, the study revealed that though there is little change, recommendations may be derived from the research, and follow-up activities may be conducted to give the students a more long-term effect from the MBSR program.

Limitations

This study has its limitations due to the chosen sampling technique that affects the external validity of findings, classes' availability, and other extraneous variables (i.e., internet connectivity, unexpected suspensions of classes due to the typhoon). This study's limitations include (1) the researchers used a purposive sampling technique, affecting the findings' generalizability. When applied to other populations, the results may not be accurate and consistent as they only focus on a specific population. (2) The initial number of students who were able to answer the consent form, pretest, and posttest was not equal, so the researchers decided to include only those who could answer all three forms.

Moreover, limitations included (3) the application of online classes, the respondents' internet connection's speed and stability were considered, and not all students could attend the synchronous sessions. Only those who attended all the synchronous sessions and completed the asynchronous sessions were included in the data analysis.

Lastly, (4) the school, which is located in Brgy. Santolan, Pasig City, was heavily affected by Typhoon Ulysses. The last session was compromised because the power lines and internet connectivity during the session were out or unstable. Due to this, the session was shifted from synchronous to asynchronous. All of the materials needed for the MBSR session were sent to the respondents via shared Google Drive to give them time to watch and do the activities at their convenience.

With this, the researchers determined that the study's limitations revolved around the implementation of online classes and other unforeseen extraneous variables (i.e., internet connectivity, unexpected suspensions of classes due to the typhoon) that come with it.

Conclusions

The study's findings revealed no significant difference in the overall academic burnout of the senior high school students of Our Lady of Perpetual Help School. Although only the exhaustion subscale reflects a statistically significant decrease in scores, whereas the disengagement subscale did not exhibit any significant change, it indicates that the program might have a targeted impact on specific aspects of burnout. This result raises the possibility that the online mindfulness-based stress reduction program could still hold promise in effectively reducing burnout among these students.

The online mindfulness-based stress reduction program can positively influence the academic burnout of the respondents, particularly the exhaustion subscale. Exhaustion can be significantly reduced through the practice of mindfulness. Thus, the MBSR program can be incorporated into the school curriculum to help students cope with the new normal. The convenience of accessing this program can aid today's limitations in psychological and mental health services.

Moreover, in understanding the academic stress that students might face alongside other personal factors such as familial relationships, socio-economic status, and access to education, it is highly encouraged that the government provide better support in taking care of mental health among learners and provide avenues where learners can comfortably share concerns.

Further, it is highly recommended that the Department of Education (DepEd) and Commission on Higher Education (CHED) further support mental health by making mental health care services more accessible by regulating support from registered psychometricians, registered psychologists, and registered guidance counselors as auxiliary services to teachers and educators.

Lastly, it is highly recommended that an addition of a mental health and well-being program similar to homeroom and guidance sessions be included in the curriculum to provide in-depth relationships among learners and educators to better engage within the academic community.

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